

Research Article

**Consumption of caffeinated Energy Drinks and their symptoms among undergraduate students from Bengaluru Rural District, India:
A cross-sectional study**

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the consumption of EDs and their symptoms among undergraduate students in two degree colleges in Bangalore, India. The data was collected via an online self-administered questionnaire. It consists of three sections to fulfil the study's objectives. Descriptive statistics were used to represent participants' socioeconomic and demographic information, daily habits, consumption of energy drinks, and side effects. The final sample size is 179, but 350 students from various higher secondary schools were initially enrolled in this study. 51.14% of the 179 undergraduate degree students who participated in this survey responded. Since a 171 undergraduate students expressed no interest in participating in our study. The primary reason why 76.53% of participants in our study drank caffeinated EDs was to refresh their moods. The majority of students (52.51) drank one can per week. For one year, almost the same amount of students take caffeinated EDs. Half of the students used alcohol, while the majority of students (60.33%) smoked. Of all students, 56.98% and 57.54%, respectively, had irregular sleep patterns. The majority of research participants (90.39%) reported experiencing particular symptoms after consuming energy drinks, as Table 3 illustrates. 30.16% experienced acidity, sleep deprivation (20.67%), headache (11.73%), omitting (5.09), elevated heart rate (32.96%), stomach pain (8.37%), and stress (10.61%), whereas 10.61% had no symptoms. The findings of this study suggested that college students' desire to try new things, stress from examinations, and parties are all contributing to the rise of caffeinated EDs in the diet, which is harmful to their health. These issues should be considered when developing regulations to safeguard young people from the health consequences and side effects of energy drinks.

Keywords: caffeinated Energy Drinks, symptoms, socioeconomic, Consumption, undergraduate students

Introduction

Caffeinated energy drinks (EDs) may include substantial amounts of caffeine, which may produce adverse health effects, such as an increased risk of cardiometabolic disorders and poor sleep quality [1–3]. Energy drinks are fortified beverages with added nutritional supplements [4,5]. These beverages contain large doses of methylxanthines (including caffeine) and other stimulants such as taurine, carbohydrates, glucuronolactone, inositol, niacin, panthenol, and B-complex vitamins and herbs. Hundreds of different brands on the market have high caffeine content, ranging from a modest 50 mg to an alarming 505 mg per can or bottle. The marketing of these drinks relies chiefly on that the natural ingredients in energy drinks supply may increase energy, alertness, improve athletic performance and concentration time, Researchers have indicated that as a result of lack of restrictions, energy drinks are aggressively marketed, appealing especially among young males seeking performance enhancement and other stimulant-related effects [6-9]. Some of these ingredients may repeatedly stimulate the nervous system, leading to harmful health consequences [10]. The consumption patterns of EDs and the hazardous use of alcohol mixed with EDs amongst undergraduate students in various countries have been well-documented [11-17]. Moreover, some studies have found a greater prevalence of ED consumption among male students,[18-20] but the results are inconclusive. There may be multiple pathways in which ED consumption impacts sleep. One plausible mechanism is the effect of caffeine present in ED. For example, ED consumption has been found to be associated with heart palpitations,[21] elevated systolic blood pressure and increased QT interval [22]—all of which may potentially affect sleep and be mediated by caffeine. Several studies in the field reported that EDs are consumed for compensating not enough sleep, boosting energy, increasing concentration during the study, driving for long periods, drinking with

alcohol to improve the taste of drinks or treating hangovers [23].

This study aimed to investigate the consumption of EDs and their symptoms among undergraduate students studying in degree colleges.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Data collection

This cross-sectional study was carried out at two degree colleges in Bangalore, India from January to December 2022 with the approval of the Institutional Review Board of M V J Medical College and Research Hospital, Hoskote, Bangalore, Karnataka, India. The data was collected via an online self-administered questionnaire. It consists of three sections to fulfil the study's objectives. The initial series of questions sought to determine the students' demographic characteristics, which included gender, age, marital status, place of residence, academic year, father's employment, and family income. The second component included information on everyday behaviors that are significant, such as the reason for drinking energy drinks, the frequency and duration of intake, smoking, physical activity, and sleep patterns. The final component contained questions about knowledge, consumption, and side effects of energy drinks. A sample size of 179 students was computed based on a 95% confidence interval with an error of no more than 5%. Undergraduate students from the degree college were requested to volunteer for the study using their college permission letter, and all participants given informed written consent.

Statistical analysis

To assure data quality, we examined all submitted questionnaires on a daily basis for mistakes and inconsistencies. The data was put into IBM SPSS (version 20). Descriptive statistics were used to compute frequency for categorical data and means (plus standard deviation [SD]) for numerical data.

Descriptive statistics were used to represent participants' socioeconomic and demographic

information, daily habits, consumption of energy drinks, and side effects.

Results and Discussion

The final sample size is 179, but 350 students from various higher secondary schools were

initially enrolled in this study. 51.14% of the 179 undergraduate degree students who participated in this survey responded. Since a 171 undergraduate students expressed no interest in participating in our study.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the degree students n=179

Characteristic	Categories	N=179	(%)
Age	18-19	65	36.31
	20-22	51	28.49
	23-24	63	35.19
gender	Male	96	53.63
	Female	83	46.36
marital status	Married	10	5.58
	Single	169	94.41
father's occupation	Job	36	20.11
	Business	72	40.22
	Farmer	54	30.16
	Laborer	17	9.49
family income (INR/month)	81000 and above	92	51.39
	40-80000	23	12.84
	20-40000	56	31.28
	Below 20000	8	4.46
Place of Residence	Rural	54	30.16
	Urban	125	69.83
Academic Year	First Year	65	36.31
	Second	51	28.49
	Third	63	31.19

179 respondents who finished the online survey reported the use of caffeinated EDs during the past 12 months. Table 1 displays the findings of the participants' behavioral and sociodemographic traits. Most of the participants were from urban areas, and the distribution of genders in degree courses was nearly equal. Most of them reported being single, 51.39% had a family income of INR 81000 or more per month, 40.22% had a business, and almost the same number of students from each class took part in the study. The participated students from different streams like science, commerce and Arts. Our results showed more consumption of energy drinks in male students than in female students.

Table 2. Energy drink & habits among degree students n=179

	Responses	N=179	%
Reason for consumption of energy drink	Curiosity (wondering about taste)	23	12.84
	Small Events like birthday	125	69.83
	When emotional stress	22	12.29
	Study Concentration	94	52.51
	To refresh the mood	137	76.53
Frequency of consumption (per week)	1 CAN	94	52.51
	2 CANS	20	11.17
	7 CANS	65	36.31
duration of consumption	>1 year	89	49.72
	< 1 year	90	50.27
smoking	Yes	108	60.33

Alcohol Consumption	No	71	39.66
	Yes	96	53.63
physical exercise	No	83	46.36
	Yes	102	56.98
Regular Sleeping	No	77	43.01
	Yes	76	42.45
	No	103	57.54

According to Table 2, the primary reason why 76.53% of participants in our study drank caffeinated EDs was to refresh their moods. The majority of students (52.51) drank one can per week. For one year, almost the same amount of students takes caffeinated EDs. Half of the students used alcohol, while the majority of students (60.33%) smoked. Of all students, 56.98% and 57.54%, respectively, had irregular sleep patterns.

Table 3. Symptoms Experienced after Consuming Energy Drinks among students (n = 179)

Symptoms	N=179	%
No Symptoms Experienced	19	10.61
Acidity	54	30.16
Sleep Deprivation	37	20.67
Headache	21	11.73
Omitting	9	5.09
Increased Heart Rate	59	32.96
Stomach pain	15	8.37
Stress	19	10.61

The majority of research participants (90.39%) reported experiencing particular symptoms after consuming energy drinks, as Table 3 illustrates. 30.16% experienced acidity, sleep deprivation (20.67%), headache (11.73%), omitting (5.09), elevated heart rate (32.96%), stomach pain (8.37%), and stress (10.61%), whereas 10.61% had no symptoms.

One of the most significant accomplishments of this study was the explanation of the motives for drinking energy drinks. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first research of its sort in the region. Our survey found that male students used more energy drinks than female students. This difference could be due to the fact that Dammam's study included students from all faculties, not just medical students, or that the number of males in their study was much higher than females (their male: female ratio was about 2.1:1), with a higher prevalence among males, or to differences in both sample sizes. Similarly, another study conducted at four medical colleges in Karachi, Pakistan reported a higher

rate (42.9%) of energy drinks consumption among medical students than that reported from our study [24]. The motivation for drinking was to have a party with friends, refresh their attitudes, and reduce tension. Previous investigations found comparable results [25-27]. From our perspective, males tend to engage in greater risks, physical activity, and careless behavior than females [29]. Similar to a prior study, unmarried students used more energy drinks, most likely because they are younger and take more risks [28-30]. As students go through their academic level, they encounter a wide range of recurring pressures connected to scholastic obligations, which push them to utilize stimulants such as energy drinks[31]. College students frequently take energy drinks for a variety of reasons, including focus, partying, and mental stress relief. The adverse effects were all reversible and showed increased neural activity. The most frequent symptom reported by consumers was an increase in heart rate. Some research indicated that energy drinks might increase

blood pressure and heart rate[32-33]. Alcohol combined with energy drinks (AmED) is more dangerous than consuming alcohol or energy drinks alone [34]. The prior research reveals that AmED connects to the use of nicotine, marijuana, and other stimulants [35] and leads to additional unfavorable outcomes, such as increased alcohol intake, unsafe sexual behaviors, and unlawful driving [36-40]. In our research, 53.63% of students consumed drink; they may have combined caffeinated ED with alcohol. Although the neurobiological processes behind the relationship between alcohol and EDs are unknown, an animal research indicated that persistent AmED intake may produce an inflammatory response, oxidative stress, and cell death in the temporal cortex and hippocampus of rats. [41] Although our study did not find a correlation between ED usage and sleep quality, we did find that the most prevalent reason for ED use was to keep alert at work. Participants associated a number of adverse effects with energy drinks; the most prevalent impacts include increased heart rate. Energy drink usage is quite common among college students in India. Our findings may raise concerns among undergraduate students about their understanding of the potential adverse consequences of these drinks. We are aware of this study's limitations. First off, the research population could not be nationally representative because it was a convenience sample of students from a particular location. Second, the short research period resulted in a restricted number of replies. It is also likely that the self-administered questionnaire has recall bias. We recommend that measures that are more thorough be created and a representative sample be gathered for future research.

Conclusion

The findings of this study suggested that college students' desire to try new things, stress from examinations, and parties are all contributing to the rise of caffeinated EDs in the diet, which is harmful to their health. These issues should be considered when developing

regulations to safeguard young people from the health consequences and side effects of energy drinks. It's crucial to raise public health knowledge, particularly among students, regarding the proper use of caffeinated beverages, their advantages, adverse effects, and correcting misconceptions. It is concerning that, the consumption of caffeinated EDs among undergraduate students appears to be associated with dangerous substances behavior, indicating a need for future health education. Health interventions that promote ED awareness among undergraduate students are recommended.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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